

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RGN 20: MEDICAL NURSING II RGN 223
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
 - Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
 - Each question carries 20marks
 - Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark*

QUESTION ONE

Mr Atobrah, a 45-year old unemployed was admitted to the male medical ward with a diagnosis of liver cirrhosis.

- a. List **FOUR (4)** types of Liver Cirrhosis. - 2 marks
- b. State **TWELVE (12)** clinical manifestations that Mr. Atobrah is likely to exhibit. - 6 marks
- c. Describe the nursing management you would render to Mr. Atobrah under the following:
 - I. Skin care - 6 marks
 - II. Nutrition - 6 marks

QUESTION TWO

Miss Zaku is a heavy cigarette smoker, who is admitted to the medical ward with Bronchiectasis.

- a. What is Bronchiectasis? - 1 mark
- b. Mention **FOUR** causes of Bronchiectasis - 4 marks
- c. Describe the pathophysiology of Bronchiectasis - 7 marks
- d. Describe the nursing management of Miss Zaku - 8 marks

QUESTION THREE

A 52-year old Mrs Boakye has lost her only child in a Road Traffic Accident. She is admitted on your ward with blood pressure of 180/110 mmHg.

- a. What type of hypertension is that of Mrs Boakye? - 1 mark
- b. Describe the pathophysiological process of Mrs Boakye's illness - 4 marks
- c. Describe the management of Mrs Boakye under the following:
 - i. Diet - 6 marks
 - ii. Stress - 4 marks
- d. Mention **FIVE** effects of hypertension on the body - 5 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Miss Faustina Mansah, aged 20 years, is on your ward, with a diagnosis of leukaemia.

- a. State **EIGHT** clinical manifestations of Leukaemia - 4marks
- b. Describe your nursing interventions based on the following nursing diagnoses:
 - i. High risk for infection related to neutropenia - 5marks
 - ii. Altered nutrition, less than body requirement related to anorexia -5marks
 - iii. High risk for bleeding related to thrombocytopenia - 6marks

INDEX NUMBER.....STUDENT'S SIGNATURE:.....

HFNMTC- BEREKUM/ST
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION, 22ND SEPTEMBER, 2021
(RGN 223) RGN 22 MEDICAL NURSING II
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Uncle Kwamena is a heavy cigarette smoker, who is admitted to the medical ward with Bronchiectasis.

- a. What is Bronchiectasis? - 1 MARK
- b. Mention **FOUR(4)** causes of Bronchiectasis - 4 MARKS
- c. Describe the pathophysiology of Bronchiectasis - 7 MARKS
- d. Describe the nursing management of Uncle Kwamena - 8 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Mr Omame Kontor, 72 years old is admitted to your ward with **Right-sided heart failure**.

- a. Explain Right-sided heart failure to a first-year student nurse - 2 MARKS
- b. Describe the pathophysiology of Right-sided heart failure - 4 MARKS
- c. Enumerate **EIGHT (8)** clinical manifestations of Mr Kontor's illness - 4 MARKS
- d. Describe the nursing management you would render to Mr Kontor - 10 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Miss Faustina Mansah, aged 20 years, is on your ward, with a diagnosis of leukaemia.

- a. State **EIGHT(8)** clinical manifestations of Leukaemia - 4MARKS
- b. Describe your nursing interventions based on the following nursing diagnoses:
 - i. High risk for infection related to neutropenia - 5MARKS
 - ii. Altered nutrition, less than body requirement related to anorexia - 5MARKS
 - iii. High risk for bleeding related to thrombocytopenia - 4MARKS
- c. Mention **TWO(2)** diagnostic investigations for leukaemia - 2MARKS

MR. ERIC OBENG

NMTC – BEREKUM
RESIT- EXAMINATION, MAY 2014
D14/RM- 9 MEDICINE & MEDICAL NURSING II
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

A fifty five (55) year old man Akwasi Oppong is on admission on your ward with a Cardiac Disorder. He suddenly develops Pulmonary Edema.

- a. Briefly describe the pathophysiology of this kind of Pulmonary Edema - 5 marks
- b. State ten (10) clinical features of pulmonary edema - 5 marks
- c. List three (3) groups (classes) of drugs and give an example each used in the management of Hypertension - 6 marks
- d. State four (4) non – pharmacological measures used in managing Hypertension - 4 marks

Question Two

A 40 year old man, John Mensah is admitted to the medical ward of the Holy Family Hospital, Berekum with the diagnosis of Leukeamia.

- a. Describe Leukeamia in your own words - 2 marks
- b. Describe the Nursing Management of Mr. Mensah under the following;
 - i. Prevention of bleeding - 5 marks
 - ii. Prevention of infection - 5 marks
- c. Briefly describe the available treatment modalities of Leukaemia - 8 marks

Question Three

- a. List two main modes of transmission of Hepatitis B - 1 mark
- b. State eight (8) risk factors of Hepatitis B - 4 marks
- c. Outline the preventive measures of Hepatitis B - 8 marks
- d. State seven (7) potential complications of Sickle Cell Disease - 7 marks

Question Four

Briefly describe the following conditions each - 4 marks

- a. Coeliac disease
- b. Afibrinogeneamia
- c. Emphysema
- d. Esophageal varices
- e. Pulmonary embolism